

Jingde chuandeng lu 景德傳燈錄

Secondary source

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** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Religious Group, Text, Chinese Buddhist text, Chan Buddhist text, Chinese Buddhism, Religious History

The Jingde chuandeng lu (Record of the Transmission of the Lamp [Compiled in] the Jingde era) was initially titled the Fozu tongcan ji 佛祖同參集 when the Buddhist monk Daoyuan 道原 (fl. ca. 1000) presented his compilation of Chan transmission records to the Song court in 1004. Daoyuan, known as a Fayan-lineage 法眼宗 monk from the Chengtian Yong'an Monastery 承天永安院 in Suzhou 蘇州, was a disciple of Tiantai Deshao 天台德韶 (891-972) who served as preceptor of the state of the Wuyue regime. It is documented that Daoyuan's compilation adopted a multilineal framework that arranged the name of 1701 figures (52 generations predicated on the master-disciple relationship) and delineated the transmission histories from the Seven Buddhas of the Past, Indian patriarchs, and eventually, to the Fayan lineage. // Under Emperor Zhenzong's 真宗 (r. 997-1022) imperial edict, leading scholarly literati Yang Yi 楊億 (974-1020), Li Wei 李維 and Wang Shu 王曙 (963-1034) supervised the editorial work of Daoyuan's compilation. According to the Xu zizhi tongjian changbian 續資治通鑑長編, the thirty-fascicle Jingde chuandeng lu was accomplished and issued in 1009. In this current title, "Jingde" refers to the reign title of Emperor Zhenzong, and "chuandeng lu" represents the way that dharma was transmitted from master to disciple similar to how one lamp lights up another. In Yang Yi's accounts, this edited compilation included the names of 1760 figures and 1169 entries. However, extant woodblock-printed editions of the Jingde chuandeng lu went through later editing and did not preserve the full text of the original records. Among varied extant editions, two main editions are the Tōji 東寺 edition (printed in 1080 in the Dongchan Monastery 東禪寺 in Fuzhou 福州) and the Sibū congkan 四部叢刊 edition (issued in 1316 in the Daochang chanyou Temple 道場禪幽庵 in Huzhou 湖州). The standard text cited in modern scholarship came from the Taishō shinshū daizōkyō 大正新修大藏經, which employed the Sibū congkan edition. Both the Tōji and Sibū congkan editions contain the name of 1709 people and 966 entries. // Entries of Chan masters in the Jingde chuandeng lu include their sermons, transmission verses, poems, and dialogues with disciples. According to recent scholarship, the compilation of this work drew on earlier Chan transmission records. The multilineal style first appeared as the arrangement format of the Zutang ji 祖堂集. The list of Indian patriarchs came from the Baolin zhuan 寶林傳. In addition to these two collections, other extant Chan genealogical histories prior to the Jingde chuandeng lu include the Chuan Fabao ji 傳法寶紀, the Lengqie shizi ji 楞伽師資記, and the Lidai Fabao ji 曆代法寶記. However, the Jingde chuandeng lu was distinct from previous Chan genealogical histories as it received imperial sanction from the Song court and had its influence transcending the regional boundaries. // In 1011, the Jingde chuandeng lu obtained Emperor Zhenzong's permission to be incorporated into the Song Buddhist canon. Another version of this work, the fifteen-fascicle abridged version compiled by scholarly bureaucrat Wang Sui 王隨 (973-1039) and titled Chuandeng yuying ji 傳燈玉英集, was submitted to Emperor Renzong 仁宗 (r. 1022-1063) in 1034 and granted to become an inclusion of the Buddhist canon as well. As the first work of the denglu (lamp records) genre, the Jingde chuandeng lu established a model for subsequent Chan genealogical histories sanctioned by the Song court, such as the Tiansheng guangdeng lu 天聖廣燈錄, the Jianzhong jingguo xudeng lu 建中靖國續燈錄, and the Jiatai pudeng lu 嘉泰普燈錄. // Besides its impact on later genealogical histories, the Jingde chuandeng lu was also involved with the development of other genres of Chan texts. Recent studies proved that cases of Chan masters compiled in later gong'an 公案 collections were initially documented in the Jingde chuandeng lu. Similarities in language styles between denglu and yulu 語錄 were also discerned. // Considering the historicity of Chan transmission records, scholars suggest that the Jingde chuandeng lu

should be viewed as didactic work that served certain religious purposes. According to existing scholarship, Daoyuan's compilation aimed at promoting the Fayan lineage. Meanwhile, Yang Yi's editing portrayed Chan as "a separate practice outside the teaching" to help provide a literary model that distinguished Song culture. With the effort of Chan monks and scholarly literati, the compilation of this work was influential in defining the self-identity of Chan.

Date Range: 1004 CE - 1004 CE

Region: Northern Song Dynasty

Region tags: Asia, East Asia

Northern Song

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Daoyuan. "Jingde chuandeng lu." In *Taishō shinshū daizōkyō*, edited by Takakusu Junjirō, Watanabe Kaigyoku, et al., Vol. 51, No. 2076. Tokyo: Taishō issaikyō kankōkai, 1988.
- Source 2: Daoyuan. *Jingde chuandeng lu*. Edited by Feng Guodong. Zhengzhou: Zhongzhou guji chubanshe, 2019.
- Source 3: Daoyuan. *Records of the Transmission of the Lamp (Jingde chuandeng lu): Volume 1 (Books 1-3), The Buddhas and Indian Patriarchs*. Translated by Randolph S. Whitfield. Norderstedt: Books on Demand, 2015. Daoyuan. *Records of the Transmission of the Lamp (Jingde chuandeng lu): Volume 2 (Books 4-9), The Early Masters*. Translated by Randolph S. Whitfield. Norderstedt: Books on Demand, 2015. Daoyuan. *Records of the Transmission of the Lamp (Jingde chuandeng lu): Volume 3 (Books 10-13), The Nanyue Huairang Lineage*. Translated by Randolph S. Whitfield. Norderstedt: Books on Demand, 2016. Daoyuan. *Records of the Transmission of the Lamp (Jingde chuandeng lu): Volume 4 (Books 14-17), The Shitou Line*. Translated by Randolph S. Whitfield. Norderstedt: Books on Demand, 2017. Daoyuan. *Records of the Transmission of the Lamp (Jingde chuandeng lu): Volume 5 (Books 18-21), Heirs of Master Xuefeng Yicun*. Translated by Randolph S. Whitfield. Norderstedt: Books on Demand, 2018. Daoyuan. *Records of the Transmission of the Lamp (Jingde chuandeng lu): Volume 6 (Books 22-26), Heirs of Tiantai Deshao, Congzhan, Yunmen*. Translated by Randolph S. Whitfield. Norderstedt: Books on Demand, 2019. Daoyuan. *Records of the Transmission of the Lamp (Jingde chuandeng lu): Volume 7 (Books 27-28), Biographies and Extended Discourses*. Translated by Randolph S. Whitfield. Norderstedt: Books on Demand, 2019. Daoyuan. *Records of the Transmission of the Lamp (Jingde chuandeng lu): Volume 8 (Books 29-30), Chan Poetry and Inscriptions*. Translated by Randolph S. Whitfield. Norderstedt: Books on Demand, 2020.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://cbetaonline.dila.edu.tw/en/T2076_001
- Source 2 URL: <http://ntireader.org/taisho/t2076.html>

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <http://kanji.zinbun.kyoto-u.ac.jp/kanseki?query=景德傳燈錄>

– Source 2 URL: <https://ctext.org/searchbooks.pl?if=en&remap=gb&searchu=景德传灯录>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: According to the preface written by Yang Yi, when compiling the Fozu tongcan ji (original name of the Jingde chuandeng lu), Daoyuan collected existing diagrams of Chan patriarchs (zutu 祖圖) and Chan masters' recorded dialogues to place these records in the order of Chan lineage. The manuscript that Daoyuan presented to the Song imperial court could be handwritten.

↳ Inked

– with Ink

– Printed with moveable type

Notes: The Jingde chuandeng lu comprised thirty fascicles when scholarly literati including Yang Yi, Li Wei, and Wang Shu completed the editorial work of Daoyuan's manuscript in 1009 CE. Extant woodblock-printed editions of this thirty-fascicle work suggest that it was largely circulated as printed copies.

↳ Number of sheets

– Bound

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Wood

↳ Species

– Specify: species that are suitable for cutting blocks, for example, pear wood (material of woodblocks for the Qianlong Buddhist Canon and the Tripiṭaka Koreana).

Notes: Reference: Park, Sang-jin. *Under the Microscope : The Secrets of the Tripitaka Koreana Woodblocks*. Translated by Ji-hyun Philippa Kim. Cambridge Scholars Publishing, 2013.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Tomb

– Field doesn't know

Cemetery

– No

Temple

– Yes

Notes: Emperor Zhenzong issued an edict to admit the Jingde chuandeng lu to the Buddhist canon in 1011 CE. As printed copies of Buddhist canon were produced in the House of Sutra-printing and bestowed to Buddhist monasteries in the Song dynasty, the Jingde chuandeng lu was preserved in Buddhist monasteries.

Shrine

– No

Altar

– No

Devotional marker

– No

Cenotaph

– No

Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– Yes

Notes: Copies of this text could be owned by literati and stored in their studying room.

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: Editions of the *Jingde chuangdeng lu* had been preserved in private libraries, such as the Tieqin tongjian Hall 鐵琴銅劍樓 owned by the Qu 瞿 family in Changshu 常熟 and the Baqian juan Hall 八千卷樓 established by the Ding 丁 family in Hangzhou.

↳ Specify

– Specify: I don't know

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Daoyuan received a reward for his compilation as Emperor Zhenzong granted one ordination certificate each year to the Buddhist monastery he was affiliated with. The engravers of the Buddhist canon printing project initiated by the imperial court were paid by the polity.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Yes

Notes: The Song court provided financial support to the House of Sutra printing situated in Buddhist monasteries.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– No

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: Scholarly literati at the Song court, led by Yang Yi, received the emperor's edict to edit and issue the Jingde chuandeng lu.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: For example, the political official Yang Yi had an affiliation with the Linji lineage and claimed himself as the dharma-heir of Guanghai Yuanlian.

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

Notes: The Song court enforced religious observance based on Confucian classics, for example, the observance of three-year mourning for one's deceased parent.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– Yes

↳ Production

– Yes

Notes: Tax exemption for supporting Buddhist monasteries was present in the Song dynasty.

↳ Storage

– Yes

↳ Study

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Specify: I don't know

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist monks were present/ in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text when the text was printed in Buddhist monastery. Reference: Du Chenghui 杜成輝.

"Songdai yinjing yuan kao 宋代印經院考." *Zhongguo shi yanjiu*, 8 (2015): 117-138.

↳ Present full-time?

– Yes

- ↳ Present part-time?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?
 - No

- ↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?
 - Yes

- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Buddhist monks engaged in activities of the House of Sutra printing were designated as different titles, such as goudang 勾當, jiaokan 校勘, and dianzhu 殿主.

- ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy?
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Buddhist Vinaya.

- ↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?
 - Yes
 - Notes: Buddhist Vinaya.

- ↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?
 - Yes
 - Notes: The Senglu si 僧錄司 (Institution for Buddhist Registry).

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Jingde chuandeng lu received imperial sanction and was incorporated in the Buddhist canon issued by the Song court.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Written in Classical Chinese. The recorded sayings collected in the Jingde chuandeng lu express the rhetorical skill of Chan teachings.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for religious professionals?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is missionary work encouraged by the text for all adherents?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– I don't know

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific time?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing located in a specific place?

– No

↳ Is normative proselytizing directed toward a specific audience?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: The Jingde chuandeng lu delineated the transmission of Chan teachings from the seven Buddhas of the past to the Fayuan lineage. Its records of Chan lineage have some points different from other genealogical histories. When Yang Yi supervised the editing of this work, he designated its character as the chuandeng lu genre and viewed Chan as "a separate practice outside the teaching" to fit for his conception of a new cultural paradigm. Reference: Welter, Albert. *Monks, Rulers, and Literati: The Political Ascendancy of Chan Buddhism*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2006.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: Records from the Jingde chuandeng lu were used in Chan monastic training between masters and disciples. Additionally, being perceived as authoritative Chan text, it was employed in Buddhist rituals for the lay followers, for example, the Qing-dynasty Water-Land ritual (according to the ritual

manual titled Fajie shengfan shuilu dazhai falun baochan 法界聖凡水陸大齋法輪寶懺).

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Notes: When preaching the teachings of previous Chan masters in the dharma hall.

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Notes: During the performance of the Water-Land ritual, the recitation of the title and introduction of this text can bring the audience with karmic merits.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ On the reciter?

– Yes

Notes: In some cases, Chan monks were awoken to enlightenment while studying the masters' sayings.

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– No

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

– Specify: The Jingde chuandeng lu was not composed to serve ritual needs. However, in the Qing dynasty Water-Land ritual, this text was employed along with other Buddhist texts to invoke divine power and help realize universal salvation.

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– Yes

Notes: For example, the Water-Land ritual in the Qing dynasty.

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Large-scale Water-Land ritual can last for seven days and nights. Participants of this ritual generally include ritual specialists, donors of the ritual, and audience from the general public.

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– Field doesn't know

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Specify: frequent

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: Records from the transmission of the lamp can be used to define Chan orthodoxy for certain purposes.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– I don't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: During the Water-Land ritual, the recitation of ritual manual was performed

simultaneously with the employment of ritual instruments and the visualization of invoked divinities or spirits.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– Yes

Notes: For example, tea.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Field doesn't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Among the multiple editions of the *Jingde chuangdeng lu*, two major extant editions are the Tōji edition and the *Sibu congkan* (The Four Branches of Literature Collection) edition. The Tōji edition was originally issued in 1080 CE by the Dongchan Monastery in Fuzhou and preserved in the Tōji in Kyoto. The *Sibu congkan* edition, produced in 1316 CE, later became the primary source for modern scholarship as it was incorporated into the *Taishō shinshu daizōkyō*. Additionally, Song scholar bureaucrat Wang Sui compiled a fifteen-fascicle abridged version titled *Chuangdeng yuying ji* (Anthology of Outstanding Treasures in the Transmission of the Lamp) in 1034 CE.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: Multiple versions of this text came into existence as both official and private printing projects carved the woodblock to print this text. Official printing projects were the printing of Buddhist canon in the Song, Yuan, Ming, and Qing dynasties. Private projects included the printing of this text in different regions, such as Taizhou and Huzhou. The editing of its contents continued in the Song and later periods.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

Notes: Difference in the sequence of certain records, the inclusion of Yang Yi's preface, and the number of fascicles, etc.

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

Notes: Existing scholarship discussed which edition might be more faithful to the original editions compiled by Daoyuan and edited by scholarly literati led by Yang Yi.

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– Yes

Notes: Through examining the material and textual information of extant editions and comparing the content with historical records (such as the prefaces written by Daoyuan and Yang Yi, and the Dazhongxiangfu fabao lu 大中祥符法寶錄).

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

Notes: The date of production is not the only criterion. Among the extant editions, the older ones are not necessarily more faithful to Daoyuan's and Yang Yi's original editions.

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Notes: Under the imperial edict of Emperor Zhenzong in 1011 CE, the Jingde chuandeng lu was

incorporated into the Song Buddhist canon.

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: Imperial sanction and religious orthodoxy.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

Notes: For example, Wang Sui's abridged edition titled *Chuangdeng yuying ji* was presented Emperor Renzong, who issued the edict to include Wang's text into the Song Buddhist canon.

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Extant Chan texts suggest that the records of Chan transmission histories (such as the *Chuan fabao ji*, *Lengqie shizi ji*, *Lidai fabao ji*, *Baolin zhuan*, and the *Zutang ji*) came into existence before the compilation of the *Jingde chuandeng lu*. While collecting sources from existing Chan records, the *Jingde chuandeng lu* was significant in being the first of a series of imperial sanctioned Chan transmission histories in the Song dynasty. Representing an influential genre of Chan texts known as "denglu (lamp records)," the *Jingde chuandeng lu* set the model for subsequent compilations of Chan transmission histories, including the *Tiansheng guangdeng lu*, *Jianzhong jingguo xudeng lu*, and the *Jiatai pudeng lu*.

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The "denglu (lamp records)" genre might draw inspiration from the Chinese literary tradition of official historiographies, especially the category of "liezhuan (biographies of exemplary individuals)."

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: I don't know

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: This text include a chronological table titled Xilai nianbiao 西來年表.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Jingde chuandeng lu presents a multilineal framework for Chan patriarchal lineages, which includes 52 generations, 1709 individuals (based on the Tōji and Sibū congkan editions). Tracing the Chan transmission histories from the seven Buddhas of the past and Indian patriarchs to Chinese Chan patriarchs, this text contributed to establishing the orthodoxy of Chan teachings.

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Student-Teacher Relationship

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Chan masters' ancient cases and transmission verses collected in this text discuss the body and

mind.

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: Chan Buddhism in the Song dynasty portrayed itself as a distinctive and independent Buddhist tradition by emphasizing the mind-to-mind transmission of Chan teachings.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

Notes: In this text, among Chan masters' interpretations of the true mind (zhenxin 真心), there are certain opinions claiming that the true mind is intrinsically empty. With the principle of non-duality, body and mind are not conceived as ontologically distinct.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– I don't know

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

Notes: Within this text, Chan masters discuss the conception of the mind that is viewed as identical to the Buddha and the division between the true mind and the deluded mind.

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally positive

↳ If associations with mental aggregates are neither positive or negative, are there other important details to know?

– Specify: In Buddhism, sentient beings are composed of the five aggregates of forms, feelings, thoughts, karmic formations, and consciousness. This text includes Chan masters' dialogues concerning awakening to the empty nature of five aggregates.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– Yes

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– I don't know

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– I don't know

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Yes

Notes: The notion of mind-body dualism became a heated debate in the Northern and Southern dynasties between Confucian literati and Buddhist monks. In general, by drawing on Buddhist concepts such as the dharma body, buddha nature, and karmic reincarnation, Buddhist monks claimed the spirit was not extinguished while the body died.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: For example, the verse "not fail to obtain human body in the next life 來生亦不失人身."

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: the cycle of samsara that consists of six realms of rebirth and realm of space outside the samara.

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

Notes: The Buddha's land, for instance, the Western Pure Land.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– Yes

Notes: The upper three realms of rebirth known as the realms of gods, asuras, and human.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– Yes

Notes: The lower three realms of rebirth known as the realms of hungry ghosts, animals, and hell.

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– Yes

↳ In human form?

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form?

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s)?

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage, etc.)?

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma)?

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world?

– Yes

Notes: In Buddhism, the six realms of rebirth provide reincarnation forms as gods, asuras, human, animals, hungry ghosts, and hell beings.

↳ In textual exegesis among practitioners are there debates about reincarnation?

– I don't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In this text, the biographical records of Chan masters indicate several types of burial, such as placing the corpse in the stupa, cremation, and water burial.

↳ Cremation?

– Yes

↳ Mummification?

– Yes

↳ Interment?

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism?

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying)?

– Yes

↳ Feeding to animals?

– No

Notes: No records in this text.

↳ Secondary burial?

– Yes

Notes: Chan monks' śarīras were collected to be stored in the stupa after cremation.

↳ Re-treatment of corpse?

– No

Notes: No records in this text.

↳ Are there specific designations for parts of corpses?

– No

↳ Could parts of corpses become transformed into partial bodily relics?

– Yes

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse?

– I don't know

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs?

– No

↳ In cemetery?

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt?

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities)?

– No

↳ Other formal burial type?

– Yes

Notes: Build stupa in Buddhist monasteries to preserve the śarīra.

↳ Other intensive funerary ritual

– Specify: funerary ritual for cremation

Notes: see details in the ritual manual titled Chapi zuofa wen 荼毗作法文 (https://tripitaka.cbeta.org/D64n9031_001).

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The "Buddha" is present in the text as the supreme high-god. Numerous Buddhas exist in the Buddhist world. In the *Jingde chuangeng lu*, the origin of Chan Buddhism is traced down to the Seven Buddhas of the past. According to the legend of the mind-to-mind transmission in Chan lineages, the Buddha Śākyamuni transmitted the dharma robe to his disciple Mahākāśyapa, who was revered as the first patriarch of Chan Buddhism.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Notes: No records in this text.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: I don't know.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world
– Yes

Notes: The cycle of samsara.

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Can reward
– Yes

|

↳ Can punish
– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion
– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion
– I don't know

↳ Possesses Hunger?
– No

↳ Can be hurt?
– No

↳ Can be tricked?
– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?
– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature
–Specify: I don't know.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living
– I don't know

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?
– Yes

Notes: For example, during the “ascending the hall” rite, Chan masters were identified as the Buddha through the affirmation of spiritual lineage, which was supported by the

multilineal framework from this text.

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?
– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?
– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?
– Yes

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?
– Yes

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).
– Yes

Notes: enlightenment

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt
– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world
– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– No

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

–Specify: I don't know.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Communicate through other means

– Specify: I don't know.

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: In the Buddhist cosmology, there are six realms of rebirth, which include the realms of gods, asuras, humans, animals, hungry ghosts and hell beings.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

↳ Know basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - I don't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - I don't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: I don't know.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– No

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: I don't know.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: After the editorial work of scholarly literati at the Song court, the *Jingde chuandeng lu* was named after the reign title "Jingde" of the Emperor Zhenzong.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No. The reproduction of this text was not in control. Both hand-written and printed copies could be found in the Song society. Historical records suggest that Song literati who read and studied this text sometimes extracted several passages to compile their distinctive versions of this text. For instance, in 1034 CE, scholarly bureaucrat Wang Sui compiled an abridged version of the *Jingde chuandeng lu*. Wang Sui offered his fifteen-fascicle *Chuandeng yuying ji* to Emperor Renzong and received imperial permission to incorporate his work into the Buddhist canon.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Destruction of the text occurred when Buddhist monasteries burned down in war.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Providing medicine to cure people, bestowing food to the hungry ghosts

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The Jingde chuangdeng lu served the didactic purpose of Chan historiography. Since certain copies of this text were preserved in Buddhist monasteries, it could be taught in Chan monasteries. The command of ancient cases and transmission verses were part of the monastic teachings for Song-dynasty Chan monks.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Notes: The multilineal transmission records compiled in this text specify the relationship between master and disciple.

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Chan disciples received the seal of enlightenment and the dharma robe from their masters to represent the transmission of the dharma.

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: cure diseases, extinguish bad karma

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: Though some sayings of Chan masters collected in this text mentioned warfare, this word was largely used as a metaphor referring to the progress of spiritual cultivation. Since the Jingde

chuandeng lu mainly served as didactic work to fulfill religious functions, its collected records might not indicate the historical reality of the past.

↳ Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

↳ Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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